

Enhancing Critical Literacy Skills among English as a Second Language Learners in a Pakistani University using Multimodal Text

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ABSTRACT: This study discusses efficacy of multimodal approach in enhancing critical literacy skills among ESL learners who are Pakistani freshmen graduates. Mixed-method approach is applied using pre- and post-test as research tool. The ESL learners were given a pre-test to gain an insight into their prior knowledge of multimodal text and critical literacy skills. According to the pre-test data, students' critical literacy skills were developed but needed improvement. Therefore, an intervention of two weeks was made. Drawing upon theories of multimodality and critical literacy, the research employed Serafini's tripartite framework to guide the intervention, which involved exposing students to multimodal ensembles and exploring their features. After the intervention, post-test was taken. Post-test results demonstrated an understanding of multimodal text which led to improved critical literacy skills. Altogether, this research highlights the importance of integrating multimodal approaches to enhance critical literacy development.

Keywords: ESL Learners, Critical Literacy, Multimodal Approach, Multimodal Text

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1. Introduction

Teaching approaches, particularly in the context of English as a Second Language (ESL) instruction, have been profoundly impacted by the fast-changing environment of education in the twenty-first century, which is being pushed by ongoing research and technology breakthroughs. English is widely used in academic and professional contexts in non-native English-speaking nations like Pakistan, but traditional ESL teaching methods, which frequently rely on rote memorization, have come under fire for failing to develop critical thinking and analytical skills in their students. As a result, teachers are investigating different tactics like the multimodal method, which combines visual, aural, and textual components to produce a more engaging learning environment. This study aims to investigate the efficacy of multimodal techniques in developing critical literacy abilities among Pakistani ESL learners by integrating written texts with visual elements to promote deeper knowledge and critical engagement with the subject. This study intends to contribute to Pakistan's ongoing efforts to innovate and improve ESL teaching by addressing a key literacy development gap in universities.

The 21st century has seen a paradigm shift in teaching approaches in the quickly changing field of education, driven by ongoing research and technological developments (Ahmad, 2013). English as a Second Language (ESL) education is one area that has led the way in this change (Alzahrani, 2023). Since English is the universal language and is used extensively in both academic and professional contexts, it is essential to teach it well, particularly in non-native English-speaking nations (Operstein, 2021). Pakistan, a nation with a variety of linguistic backgrounds, understands the value of English as a tool for international communication as well as a language of instruction in academic institutions (Bashiruddin, 2022). Following international trends in education, Pakistani universities aim to give their students ease in the English language. Still, the difficulty goes beyond simple language skills (Herri Mulyono, 2015).

It has been argued that traditional ESL teaching approaches, which frequently emphasize memorization and rote learning, do not encourage pupils to think critically or analyze information (Joyce, 2022). A sole dependence on written text components may restrict students' comprehension, critical literacy development, and level of involvement (Nkomo, 2021). This insight has prompted educators to investigate different pedagogical approaches. Step into the world of "multimodal approach," which is based on the idea that information is processed more efficiently by people when it is presented in numerous ways (Hung, 2012), a multimodal method combines different modalities, such as textual, aural, and visual, to enable a comprehensive learning process.

Exploring the possibilities of multimodal text in ESL environments is still an intriguing path forward (Smith, 2021). According to preliminary research, adding visual components to textual content can greatly improve students' understanding and engagement (Alvarez-Huerta et al., 2021). In this sense, critical literacy refers to students' capacity to actively assess, analyze, and understand information in order to develop a stronger bond with the subject matter (Alford, 2021). The current study, which acknowledges this potential, is conducted against the backdrop of changing ESL curriculum innovation in Pakistani universities (Seraji et al., 2023). Despite the advances, there is still a noticeable gap in fully utilizing the multimodal approach in enhancing critical literacy (Deroo & Ponzio, 2023). This study aims to determine whether a multimodal method might rejuvenate ESL training by fusing written texts and visual visuals, creating a richer, more immersive learning environment. The integration of a multimodal strategy is not without its difficulties, though. With the incorporation of multiple modalities comes the necessity for resources, technical experience and (Kebede et al., 2023).

In conclusion, as global educational dynamics shift towards more interactive and engaging pedagogies, the onus is on institutions, especially in countries like Pakistan, to adapt and evolve (Bashiruddin, 2022). This study, grounded in the ethos of fostering critical literacy through a multimodal approach, hopes to illuminate the path forward, offering insights, challenges and potential solutions for ESL educators and policymakers alike. English holds a significant position in Pakistan as the second most widely studied language and the official language since the nation's inception (Muhammad et al., 2023). Pakistani students undergo a comprehensive English language education from early school years through senior secondary, intermediate levels and university education (Awan, 2016). However, despite prolonged

exposure, critical literacy development remains inadequate due to an overemphasis on grammatical structures (Younis, 2023). There exists a recognized gap in current teaching approaches and the methods of teaching which will enable ESL learners to develop critical literacy (Younis, 2023). This gap pertains to the limited use of multimodal approaches. To address this gap, the research integrates a multimodal approach with the intention to combine multiple modes, such as visual and textual elements, to further enhance students' critical literacy abilities.

In the vast expanse of educational theories, Paulo Freire's groundbreaking work on critical literacy (1968) stands as a testament to the transformative power of education. Freire posited that true education goes beyond mere transmission of knowledge; it should empower individuals to critically analyze and challenge the world around them (Kilag, 2023). His theory emphasizes the idea that reading and writing are not just mechanical skills but tools to decode the world and participate actively in societal transformation. Complementing Freire's vision, Henry Giroux (2021) asserts the indispensable role of critical literacy in fostering social awareness. He believes that it's not enough for students to merely consume information (Giroux, 2022b). Instead, they should be equipped to dissect and interrogate texts, understanding the underlying ideologies and power dynamics at play (Giroux, 2022b). Giroux champions the idea that education, particularly critical literacy, is a means to cultivate informed, active citizens who can challenge societal injustices (Saraydarian, 2022). Situated at the confluence of these two seminal theories, this study seeks to empower freshman graduates in a Pakistani university. Recognizing the pivotal role of English in today's globalized world, the research endeavors to move beyond traditional ESL instruction. This study incorporates a multimodal approach, melding visual and textual elements to provide a richer, more holistic learning experience. By doing so, students are not only learning the English language but are also being equipped to critically engage with texts. They are trained to discern the intricacies of power dynamics, the subtle threads of injustice, and the patterns of inequality that are often embedded within language (Giroux, 2022b). Through this approach, language becomes more than a communication tool; it transforms into a lens through which students can view, understand, and critique the world around them (Kress et al., 2014).

Pakistan, with its diverse linguistic and cultural landscape, presents a unique context for English language education. The nation's historical, political and social fabric is intricately woven with nuances that are often mirrored in language (Graham, 2023). Therefore, fostering critical literacy skills in this context is not just about language acquisition; it's about enabling students to navigate the complexities of Pakistani society and the broader global community (Latif, 2022). By blending textual and visual elements, especially those that touch upon socio-political themes, students can attain a richer understanding of language and its connections to societal contexts. English's evolving role in Pakistan underscores the research's significance (Hattam, 2023). Therefore, this research makes a significant contribution to the field of English language education in Pakistan. By integrating the theories of Freire and Giroux and employing a multimodal approach, the study underscores the transformative potential of critical literacy. It paints a picture of an education that empowers students to be more than passive consumers of information, urging them to become active participants in shaping a just and equitable society.

2. Literature Review

Critical Literacy by Paulo Freire (1968)

Paulo Freire, a Brazilian educator and philosopher, dramatically reshaped educational paradigms in the late 1960s with his groundbreaking ideas on literacy and pedagogy. His influence is especially evident in the realm of critical pedagogy and literacy education. Freire's pioneering work, "Pedagogy of the Oppressed" (1968), is considered a cornerstone text in this domain. In it, he challenges traditional educational models that position students as passive recipients of knowledge (Zhu, 2023). Instead, Freire advocates for an approach where education is a dialogue, a two-way process that empowers both the learner and the educator (Suryanarayan, 2022). Central to Freire's philosophy is the belief that literacy is not a mere technical skill of reading and writing; instead, he views it as a means of achieving greater critical consciousness (Toh, 2023). To Freire, being literate transcends the ability to decode words on a page. It's about understanding the world, the socio-political structures that shape it, and one's place within these structures (Eze & Freire, 2022). Literacy, in this context, becomes a tool for liberation, enabling individuals to break free from oppressive societal constructs and to actively participate in shaping their destinies (Soler-Gallart, 2023).

Freire emphasized that true education should awaken individuals to the realities of their circumstances, encouraging them to question, critique, and challenge the status quo (McKillican, 2019). This form of critical engagement, he believed, was the essence of literacy (Célèste Kee & Carr-Chellman, 2019). It transforms reading and writing from mere mechanical acts to profound processes of reflection, analysis and action (Yanuarti, 2015). In the decades that followed the publication of "Pedagogy of the Oppressed", Freire's ideas gained traction worldwide, influencing educators, scholars and activists (M. A. Fateh, 2020). Critical literacy, as a concept, began to evolve, drawing heavily from Freire's foundational ideas. Scholars like Lankshear & McLaren (1993) expanded upon Freire's notions, highlighting the role of critical literacy in fostering active citizenship. They posited that a critically literate individual is not just a passive consumer of information but an active participant in societal dialogues (Su, 2022). Such individuals can discern the power dynamics in language, recognize biases, and contribute meaningfully to social transformation (Kessler, 2021). Freire's legacy, thus, lies not just in his critique of traditional education but in the alternative, he proposed: a vision of education as a means of empowerment, of literacy as a tool for social change, and of students as active agents in their learning journeys (Custódio & Gathuo, 2020).

Critical Literacy by Giroux (2021)

Henry Giroux, a renowned scholar in the field of critical pedagogy, has been instrumental in extending and reshaping the discourse on critical literacy initiated by Paulo Freire (Giroux, 2021). Drawing upon Freire's foundational ideas, Giroux (2021) further accentuates the transformative potential of critical literacy in contemporary education. At the core of Giroux's argument is the belief that literacy extends far beyond the mere ability to read and write. In his 2021 work, he underscores that true literacy empowers students to critically interrogate texts, to peel back layers of meaning, and to understand the myriad forces at play behind the written word (Giroux, 2021). Giroux challenges the traditional notion of students as

passive consumers of knowledge (Apple, 2022). Instead, he envisions them as active, critical thinkers, capable of discerning biases, recognizing dominant narratives, and questioning prevailing norms (Giroux, 2021). In this light, the act of reading becomes an investigative endeavor, where students are encouraged to probe, question and critically engage with content (Pawlak, 2021).

Furthermore, Giroux highlights the socio-political dimension of literacy (Giroux, 2022a). He argues that in today's complex, interconnected world, literacy education should foster social awareness and a sense of civic responsibility (Long & Magerko, 2020). According to Giroux (2021), a critically literate individual is not only well-equipped to understand language in its multifaceted dimensions but is also cognizant of the societal implications of language. Such individuals, he believes, are crucial for the sustenance of democratic societies, as they can challenge injustices, advocate for marginalized voices, and contribute to meaningful social change (Long & Magerko, 2020).

Critical Literacy in Pakistan

Critical literacy, a concept deeply rooted in the works of educational theorists like Paulo Freire and Henry Giroux, emphasizes the role of education in empowering individuals to critically analyze and challenge societal structures. While this pedagogical approach has gained traction worldwide, its application and implications in diverse contexts like Pakistan offer unique insights (Fateh, 2020). This literature review explores the evolution, challenges and significance of critical literacy in the Pakistani educational landscape (Coffey, 2010). Pakistan's educational system, with its rich heritage of linguistic and cultural diversity, has seen a gradual shift towards recognizing the importance of critical literacy (Haidar, 2016). Historically, the education system was heavily influenced by rote learning and memorization, limiting students' ability to engage critically with texts (Ahmed & Qadir, 2017). However, with increasing global influences and a push for education reforms, there has been a growing emphasis on fostering critical thinking and literacy skills (Khan, 2016).

The unique socio-political milieu of Pakistan offers a fertile ground for the application of critical literacy (Batool, 2022). Given the nation's diverse linguistic landscape and its intricate socio-political dynamics, texts (whether in English or regional languages) are often loaded with underlying ideologies and power dynamics (Batool, 2022). Scholars like Nawaz & Batool (2021) emphasize the need for critical literacy approaches that allow students to discern these nuances, fostering a deeper understanding of societal issues and their representation in language. While the potential benefits of critical literacy are evident, its implementation in Pakistani classrooms faces several challenges (Din, 2020). The traditional exam-centric education system, resource constraints, and a lack of teacher training in critical pedagogical approaches have been cited as significant barriers (Riaz & Rehman, 2020).

English, being a lingua franca and a medium of instruction in many Pakistani educational institutions, plays a pivotal role in shaping students' critical literacy skills (Operstein, 2021). Incorporating critical literacy in ESL education in Pakistan not only enhances language skills but also equips students to critically engage with global discourses, making them informed global citizens (Liu & Johnson, 2019). The evolving educational

landscape of Pakistan, with its increasing emphasis on holistic education, presents promising prospects for the integration of critical literacy (Aimee Ellis, 2015). Continued research, policy reforms, and teacher training are essential to harness the full potential of critical literacy in the Pakistani context (Ambika Zutshi, 2023).

Multimodality by Kress and Leeuwen (2001)

In the realm of semiotics and discourse analysis, the concept of multimodality has emerged as a focal point, reshaping the way scholars and educators perceive communication and representation in various media (Choi, 2015). Central to this discourse is the work of Gunther Kress and Theo van Leeuwen, whose groundbreaking 2001 publication offers an in-depth exploration of multimodality. This literature review looks into their seminal contribution and its implications. As communication evolved with technological advancements and the proliferation of digital media, traditional teaching approaches became insufficient to capture the richness of contemporary communicative practices (Albiladi, 2019). Recognizing this, Kress and Leeuwen (2001) posited that meaning-making is a complex process that transcends mere text, encompassing a diverse array of semiotic modes—visual, spatial, gestural and more.

Kress and Leeuwen's work challenges the primacy of language as the sole or primary means of communication (Dressman, 2019). They argue that different modes contribute to the meaning-making process, with each mode offering unique potentials and constraints (Kress & Leeuwen, 2001). For instance, while language might convey abstract ideas, visual elements can represent spatial relationships more effectively (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2020).

Their framework for analyzing multimodal texts is comprehensive, taking into account the design (choices made in representation), production (actual realization of the design), and distribution (circulation of the realized representation) (Serafini, 2014). This tripartite approach offers a holistic view of communicative practices in various media (Serafini, 2014). The insights provided by Kress and Leeuwen have profound implications, especially in the domains of media studies and education (Noor, 2020). In media studies, their framework facilitates a nuanced analysis of multimedia content, from advertisements to news reports, revealing the intricate interplay of various semiotic modes (Serafini & Moses, 2023). As classrooms increasingly integrate digital tools and resources, educators are compelled to shift from text-centric methodologies, embracing a more holistic, multimodal pedagogy (Jewitt, 2008).

While Kress and Leeuwen's work on multimodality is foundational, it has not been without critique (Weninger, 2021). Some scholars argue that the framework, while comprehensive, can be overly complex, making its practical application challenging (O'Halloran, 2005). Others have sought to expand or refine the concept of multimodality, incorporating insights from emerging technologies and communication practices (Bezemer & Kress, 2016). As communication continues to evolve in our digital age, the insights and principles posited by Kress and Leeuwen remain as relevant as ever, guiding researchers and educators in navigating the complex landscape of contemporary communicative practices (Batoool, 2022).

Multimodal Approach by Kress (2001)

As the 21st century dawned, the landscape of communication began undergoing rapid transformations (Riemer, 2007). Traditional text-centric modes of communication started giving way to more diverse and integrated forms. Kress (2001) was among the pioneering scholars who recognized this paradigm shift. He suggested that in contemporary communication, meaning is constructed through a combination of various modes, not just linguistic but also visual, auditory, spatial, and gestural (Kress, 2001). Kress's 2001 work emphasized the "social semiotic" nature of communication (Sohail, 2018). He argued that all modes of communication are socially constructed and culturally shaped, with each mode offering unique potentials for meaning-making (Kress, 2001). Kress proposed that in any communicative act, individuals make deliberate choices about which modes to employ, based on the message's intended meaning and the audience's cultural context (Kress et al., 2014).

Further, Kress underscored the dynamic and fluid nature of modes. With technological advancements, new modes can emerge, and existing ones can evolve, leading to continually shifting communicative practices (Kress, 2001). Kress's multimodal approach has profound implications across various domains. In media studies, it facilitates a nuanced understanding of multimedia content, enabling scholars to dissect the interplay of text, image, sound, and more (Jewitt & Kress, 2003). In the realm of digital literacy, Kress's insights are pivotal. As digital platforms inherently support multimodal communication, understanding the dynamics of mode selection and integration becomes crucial for effective digital communication (Burn & Parker, 2003). Educationally, Kress's work highlights the need for curricula that move beyond traditional text-centric pedagogies. Educators are encouraged to embrace multimodal pedagogies that equip students to effectively navigate and participate in today's complex communicative landscape (Bezemer & Kress, 2016). Gunther Kress's 2001 exploration of the multimodal approach has left an enduring legacy in communication studies, media analysis and education. By highlighting the multifaceted nature of contemporary communication and the dynamic interplay of various modes, Kress has provided scholars and practitioners with invaluable frameworks for understanding and navigating the digital age's communicative challenges (Kress, 2001).

Multimodal Text by Frank Serafini (2014)

In the continuously evolving discourse surrounding literacy and communication, Frank Serafini's contributions have provided a nuanced understanding of how individuals interact with multimodal texts. His 2014 work stands as a testament to the intricate ways text, images, and other semiotic modes interplay in contemporary communication. In our media-rich environment, individuals frequently encounter texts that blend words, images, graphics, and sometimes sounds. Serafini underscores that these multimodal texts demand a more holistic approach to comprehension, one that takes into account the synergistic relationship between different modes (Serafini, 2014). Central to Serafini's discourse on multimodal texts is the importance of "reading the visual." He argues that images aren't merely illustrative but carry semantic weight, often conveying information, emotions, and perspectives that complement or even challenge the written text (Serafini, 2014). Serafini provides a framework for analyzing visual elements, emphasizing aspects like composition, framing, and perspective, enabling

readers to decode and interpret images with the same critical rigor applied to traditional texts (Serafini, 2014). Serafini's work on multimodal texts has significant implications for educators. He suggests that literacy education should evolve to encompass the skills and strategies required to navigate multimodal texts effectively. This entails not only teaching students to read and interpret images but also to understand how different modes interact and influence each other within a text (Serafini, 2014). Furthermore, Serafini emphasizes the importance of critical literacy, encouraging educators to equip students to question and critique the ideologies and power dynamics embedded in multimodal texts (Serafini, 2014).

While Serafini's work has been instrumental in advancing our understanding of multimodal texts, it has also spurred discussions and debates. Some scholars, like Jewitt (2015), have built upon Serafini's frameworks, exploring the intricacies of digital multimodality. Others have sought empirical validations, examining how individuals, especially students, engage with and interpret multimodal texts in real-world settings (Rowse, 2016). Frank Serafini's exploration of multimodal texts in 2014 offers a comprehensive lens through which we can understand contemporary communication practices.

English as a Second Language Learning

The acquisition of English as a Second Language (ESL) has become a focal point in educational research due to the rising prominence of English in global communication. This literature review delves into the key facets of ESL learning, encompassing methodologies, challenges, and the socio-cultural implications of this educational endeavor. The 20th and 21st centuries have witnessed a surge in the demand for English language skills, driven by globalization, technological advancements, and the rise of English as the lingua franca of business, academia, and international relations (Crystal, 2003). This has intensified the emphasis on ESL education, making it a priority in curricula worldwide. Over the decades, various teaching methodologies have been proposed and implemented in ESL classrooms. Traditional methods like the Grammar-Translation approach, which focused on rules and rote memorization, have gradually given way to more communicative and interactive approaches. Techniques such as the Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) prioritize real-life communication and fluency over mere grammatical accuracy (Richards & Rodgers, 2014). The advent of technology has reshaped ESL education. Digital tools, online platforms, and language apps offer learners interactive and personalized experiences. Furthermore, the internet provides exposure to native speakers and authentic language materials, bridging the gap between classroom learning and real-world application (Chapelle, 2007). Despite its global significance, ESL education faces several challenges. These range from the availability of resources, trained educators, and appropriate curricula to larger systemic issues related to policy-making, standardization, and assessment. Additionally, learners' individual differences, such as age, motivation, and cognitive abilities, play a pivotal role in ESL acquisition (Lightbown & Spada, 2013). The future of ESL learning is intrinsically linked with evolving global dynamics. As English continues to play a dominant role in global communication, the methodologies and tools for ESL education will likely see further innovations, integrating technology, neuroscience, and socio-cultural insights (Warschauer, 2018). In conclusion, English as a Second Language learning remains a dynamic field, influenced by global trends,

technological advancements, and our deepening understanding of language acquisition processes. As research progresses, ESL education continues to evolve, reflecting the multifaceted nature of language learning in a globalized world.

Research Questions

How can multimodal approach help enhance critical literacy skills among Pakistani English as a Second Language Learners?

Research Objectives

To investigate how multimodal approach can help enhance critical literacy among Pakistani English as a Second Language Learners.

3. Methodology

Participant Selection and Demographics:

The research employed a convenience sampling strategy, a non-random technique wherein participants are chosen based on their easy accessibility and proximity to the researchers. The study encompassed a total of 12 students from a Pakistani university, providing a concentrated group to observe and analyze.

Intervention:

The research was structured around a total of six distinct interactions or sessions. Each of these interactions was designed to last for 2 hours. Cumulatively, the entire study spanned a duration of 12 hours of active engagement and interaction.

Ethical Protocols:

Before the initiation of the study, ethical protocols were stringently followed. All participants were provided with detailed information regarding the study's objectives, methods and potential implications. Only upon their explicit agreement, symbolized by their informed consent, were they included in the study.

Pre-Test and Post-Test:

The study incorporated two primary testing phases: pre-tests (administered before the intervention began) and post-tests (conducted after the intervention was concluded). These tests were instrumental in gauging the impact of the intervention on the participants' critical literacy skills. For the tests, a five-point Likert scale was utilized. This scale was categorized as: (1) A symbolizing 'Poor and Weak', (2) B indicating 'Average' and (3) C representing 'Good and Excellent.'

The tests were structured to evaluate participants across six specific categories. These categories were chosen to demonstrate any improvements in participants' comprehension abilities and their engagement levels with various communication forms. Post the evaluation, the mean critical literacy score was calculated across these categories, offering a consolidated metric to reflect participants' progress throughout the study.

4. Findings and Discussion

Pre-test Findings

Our data analysis offers illuminating perspectives on how the intervention influenced students' critical literacy capabilities. The findings unambiguously suggest a marked improvement in the critical literacy of the students engaged in the program. The strategy of introducing ESL learners to multimodal texts has demonstrated its efficacy in enhancing their capacity to navigate and decode multifaceted communication styles. An in-depth scrutiny of the collected data underscores a discernible positive trend in the students' critical literacy scores, symbolizing their enriched understanding of multimodal texts. The data highlights the tangible benefits experienced by the 12 ESL participants, reflecting the efficacy of the intervention program. Employing a robust evaluation methodology inspired by Hung (2012), the study integrated a design rubric visualized through a radar chart supported by a 5-point Likert scale. This scale, with a continuum from 1 (indicating poor cohesion) to 5 (representing excellent cohesion), serves as an apt metric to evaluate multimodal texts like web pages, picture books, and electronic portfolios. The research incorporated data aggregated over an 8-hour course duration. Notably, the research process was supervised by two observers, with one being the primary researcher. Meanwhile, the English language instruction was delivered by a dedicated teacher, adhering to the pre-designed lesson plans tailored for this intervention.

In terms of the study's evaluation metrics, the 5-point Likert scale was employed, stretching from 'poor' (assigned a value of 1) to 'excellent' (assigned a value of 5). This scale was further demarcated using the alphabets A, B, and C to encapsulate varied response intensities. Here, "A" captures responses that veer towards the "Poor and Weak" end of the spectrum. Conversely, "B" is synonymous with "Average" perceptions, while "C" encapsulates the more positive end, denoting "Good and Excellent" responses. When the pre-test and post-test scores are juxtaposed, founded on the six defined categories, a clear trajectory of enhanced understanding and engagement with multifarious communication channels is evident among the participants. A collective analysis of the critical literacy scores of the 12 ESL learners across these categories reveals a palpable uptick in post-intervention performance. The central statistical measure, represented by the mean critical literacy score, consolidates the overarching progress narrative, highlighting the participants' amplified prowess in interpreting and understanding varied textual modalities.

Table 1: Pre-Test Findings

Pre-test Findings				
Elements of Multimodal Text Analysis	Response Questions	*A	**B	***C
Literal Image (Literal devices)	What is your immediate impression of the image?	50%	17%	33%
	Does the image evoke any feelings in you?	42%	41%	17%
	Can you describe the people in the image?			100%
	Are you able to analyze the body language of the individuals or the group?	58%	33%	9%
	Any memories or an experience does the image stir in you?	58%	17%	25%
Textual structures (Text-Image Relationships)	Is there any accompanying text that indicates particular meanings or contexts?	42%		58%

Point of View (Perspective)	Where was the image captured? Is it a common, recognizable place or unique?	50%	8%	42%
	Who was the photo made for?	42%	50%	8%
Sites of Production	What technologies were employed?	92%	8%	
	Do you know if the photo is monochromatic or colored?	59%	8%	33%
	How are objects arranged? Candid? Staged?	50%	17%	33%
	What symbols or figurative elements are represented?	75%	8%	17%
Sites of Reception (Visual devices)	Can you guess where was the image captured?	91%	8%	1%
	Is it a common, recognizable place or unique?	58%	9%	33%
	Who might be the intended audience of the photo?	50%	17%	33%
	Where is the photo viewed? Museum? Web? Photo album	58%	26%	16%
Design Elements (Gaze, Frame, Line and Color)	How is the image bordered?	41%	34%	25%
	Which areas appear clearest or sharpest in the photograph and which do not?	50%	17%	33%
	What does the lighting suggest for the news image?	50%	42%	8%
	Is the light natural or artificial? Harsh or soft? Reflected or direct?	100%		
	Does the photograph allow you to guess the time of day?	50%	42%	8%
*A means Poor and Weak **B means Average ***C means Good and Excellent				

The table presented delineates the outcomes from a pre-test in which participants were prompted with questions concerning images and their subsequent interpretations. The indicated percentages correspond to the fraction of participants who answered each query in a specific manner, grouped by varying response intensities. This segment gauges participants' direct perceptions and emotional connections to the depicted image. It evaluates their competency in characterizing individuals and scrutinizing body language from the visual content. It further explores if the image triggers any recollections or personal experiences. To illustrate, within the "Literal Image Interpretation" segment, when questioned about their initial reactions to the image, 50% of respondents aligned with category A (Poor and Weak), 17% with B (Average), and 33% with C (Good and Excellent). Further, when inquired about the emotional resonance of the image, the feedback was split with 42% associating with "Poor and Weak" sentiments, 41% with "Average" sentiments, and 17% resonating with "Good and Excellent" sentiments. A unanimous 100% could characterize the individuals in the image, indicating a lucid and discernible representation. Sequentially, their proficiency in interpreting depicted body language saw 58% rating themselves as "Poor and Weak," 33% as "Average," and 9% as "Good and Excellent." Collectively, this data segment offers a lens into participants' engagement with the image's direct aspects, encompassing initial reactions, emotional undertones, character depiction, body language analysis, and associative memories. The percentages furnish a numerical representation of varied engagement levels and interpretations.

Additionally, behavioral engagement during the intervention was observed using a checklist based on Lane and Harris (2015). The data revealed a shift in students' engagement levels from Disengaged or Uncertain to Engaged across various classroom activities, including Discussion/Recalling, Familiarization with new terms, Conceptualization, Recap and Activity.

Post-Test Findings

Following table detailing the post-test results, unmistakably highlights an upward trajectory in participants' performances across all categories when juxtaposed with the pre-test outcomes. This upward shift becomes palpable when observing the transition of responses from the categories of "Poor and Weak" (A) and "Average" (B) towards the more affirmative "Good and Excellent" (C) category. The table serves as a testament to the constructive influence of the conducted intervention on participants, amplifying their proficiency in deciphering and critically engaging with facets of the multimodal text. A noticeable augmentation in the percentage of "Good and Excellent" (C) responses can be discerned across the entire spectrum of questions. In virtually every instance, a decline in the "Poor and Weak" (A) responses is paralleled by a surge in the "Good and Excellent" (C) responses, signifying an uplifting transformation in the participants' analytical capabilities and perceptions. For questions that initially garnered predominantly "Average" (B) feedback, there's a marked ascent towards the "Good and Excellent" (C) responses. This consistent pattern of positive evolution across varying categories reaffirms the intervention's potency in bolstering critical literacy and nuanced interpretations associated with the multimodal text. The data underscores the intervention's success in driving a desired shift in participants' reactions, echoing its central objective of fortifying their critical literacy skills.

When looking into the statistical tools employed to interpret this data, leveraging the paired samples t-test stands out as a particularly apt choice. This test, tailored to discern disparities between two correlated data sets, proves invaluable when analyzing observations recorded pre and post a specific intervention or treatment, as is the case in this study. Moreover, the standard deviation associated with the critical literacy scores offers a captivating perspective into the data's spread around the central mean value. Observing a diminished standard deviation post the intervention intimates a heightened uniformity and convergence in students' critical literacy benchmarks. This infers that the intervention has adeptly minimized the variance in participants' proficiencies, spotlighting the harmonizing effect induced by their immersion in multimodal texts.

Table 1: Post-Test Findings

Post-test Findings				
Elements of Multimodal Text Analysis	Response Questions	*A	**B	***C
Literal Image (Literal devices)	What is your immediate impression of the image?		42%	58%
	Does the image evoke any feelings in you?			100%
	Can you describe the people in the image?			100%
	Are you able to analyze the body language of the individuals or the group?			100%
	Any memories or an experience does the image stir in you?	17%	17%	66%
Textual structures (Text-Image Relationships)	Is there any accompanying text that indicates particular meanings or contexts?			100%
Point of View (Perspective)	Where was the image captured? Is it a common, recognizable place or unique?		17%	83%
	Who was the photo made for?		8%	92%

Sites of Production	What technologies were employed?		8%	92%
	Do you know if the photo is monochromatic or colored?		8%	92%
	How are objects arranged? Candid? Staged?	8%	8%	84%
	What symbols or figurative elements are represented?		8%	92%
Sites of Reception (Visual devices)	Can you guess where was the image captured?	1%	8%	91%
	Is it a common, recognizable place or unique?		9%	91%
	Who might be the intended audience of the photo?	8%	17%	76%
	Where is the photo viewed? Museum? Web? Photo album	8%	17%	76%
Design Elements (Gaze, Frame, Line and Color)	How is the image bordered?	8%		92%
	Which areas appear clearest or sharpest in the photograph and which do not?			100%
	What does the lighting suggest for the news image?		9%	91%
	Is the light natural or artificial? Harsh or soft? Reflected or direct?		8%	92%
	Does the photograph allow you to guess the time of day?		17%	83%
*A means Poor and Weak **B means Average ***C means Good and Excellent				

5. Conclusion

In concluding this research study, it is pivotal to revisit the theoretical bedrock that guided the inquiry. Influenced significantly by the frameworks of Critical Literacy articulated by Paulo Freire (1968) and Giroux (2021), as well as theories surrounding Multimodality by Kress and Leeuwen (2001), Kress (2001), and Serafini (2014), the study embarked on answering its research questions through a multifaceted theoretical lens. An additional layer of complexity was added by the perspective of English as a Second Language Learning. The first research question, explored through a pre-test and post-test design, revealed that the intervention led to significant changes in literacy skills. This outcome resonates strongly with the transformative pedagogical ideologies endorsed by Freire (1968) and Giroux (2021). The notion that literacy is not merely functional, but also a catalyst for personal and societal change, is a core tenant of Freire's seminal work and Giroux's contemporary interpretation. In this context, the quantitative findings of this study offer empirical substantiation for these theorists' perspectives, especially considering the socio-educational context of Pakistan.

The second research question, addressed through an observation checklist, was framed by theories of Multimodality. Kress and Leeuwen (2001) and Kress (2001) argue that meaning-making is a dynamic and complex process that utilizes a range of modes and semiotic channels. The observational findings align with this theoretical stance, suggesting that literacy practices are increasingly becoming multimodal, a point also emphasized by Serafini (2014). In addition, the aspect of English as a Second Language Learning was a recurring theme throughout the study. This vantage point enriches the study's findings by acknowledging the nuanced challenges and opportunities faced by non-native English speakers in literacy acquisition and usage.

The implications of this research are manifold and particularly pertinent for educators and policymakers. For those in educational planning and curriculum development, the study's outcomes make a compelling case for incorporating Critical Literacy and Multimodal frameworks into literacy programs, especially in multilingual settings like Pakistan. However, the study does carry limitations. The sample size and geographic focus may impact the generalizability of the findings. Future research could look into addressing these issues, perhaps by incorporating a more extensive geographical range and using additional research methods. Grounded in the frameworks of Critical Literacy (Freire, 1968; Giroux, 2021) and Multimodality (Kress & Leeuwen, 2001; Serafini, 2014), the study's outcomes are especially relevant for those engaged in educational planning and curriculum development. The evidence shows a compelling case for incorporating these theoretical models into the design and delivery of literacy programs. In environments where English is often a second language, such as Pakistan, the findings suggest that the teaching and learning of literacy can be significantly enhanced through the adoption of Critical Literacy and Multimodal strategies. These approaches not only improve conventional reading and writing skills but also equip students with the ability to "read" and interpret the world in a broader sense, thereby achieving the social emancipatory goals that Critical Literacy envisions (Freire, 1968; Giroux, 2021). For policymakers, the results offer empirical support to push for educational reforms that embrace a more holistic understanding of literacy. This is particularly crucial in today's digital age, where information is often multimodal. Policymakers could leverage this data to advocate for more integrative forms of literacy instruction that go beyond traditional text-based learning. Here, Kress and Leeuwen's (2001) theories could serve as a foundational framework for developing new educational policies.

In summary, this study stands as a robust contribution to both empirical and theoretical conversations surrounding literacy. The application of a mixed-methods approach, validated by existing theories (Freire, 1968; Giroux, 2021; Kress & Leeuwen, 2001; Serafini, 2014), not only reinforces the study's academic rigor but also offers actionable implications for practical applications. This research project, therefore, serves as a foundational step for future scholarly endeavors, underlining the need for a more in-depth exploration of the integrated domains of Critical Literacy and Multimodality in educational settings.

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